

Elementary Abelian Regular Coverings of Cube

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Abstract: For a give finite connected graph Γ , a group H of automorphisms of Γ and a finite group A , a natural question can be raised as follows: Find all the connected regular coverings of Γ having A as its covering transformation group, on which each automorphism in H can be lifted. In this paper, we classify all the connected regular covering graphs of the cube satisfying the following two properties: (1) the covering transformation group is isomorphic to the elementary Abelian p -groups; (2) the group of fibre-preserving automorphisms acts edge-transitively.

Key Words: Connected graph, graph covering, cube, Smarandachely covering, regular covering.

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§1. Introduction

All graphs considered in this paper are finite, undirected and simple. For a graph Γ , we use $V(\Gamma)$, $E(\Gamma)$, $A(\Gamma)$ and $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ to denote its vertex set, edge set, arc set and full automorphism group, respectively. For any $v \in V(\Gamma)$, by $N(v)$ we denote the neighborhood of v in Γ . For an arc $(u, v) \in A(\Gamma)$, we denote the corresponding undirected edge by uv .

A graph $\tilde{\Gamma}$ is called a *covering* of the graph Γ with projection $p : \tilde{\Gamma} \rightarrow \Gamma$ if there is a surjection $p : V(\tilde{\Gamma}) \rightarrow V(\Gamma)$ such that $p|_{N(\tilde{v})} : N(\tilde{v}) \rightarrow N(v)$ is a bijection for any vertex $v \in V(\Gamma)$ and $\tilde{v} \in p^{-1}(v)$. The graph $\tilde{\Gamma}$ is called the *covering graph* and Γ is the *base graph*. A $p : \tilde{\Gamma} \rightarrow \Gamma$ is called to be a *Smarandachely covering* of Γ if there exist $u, v \in V(\Gamma)$ such that $|p^{-1}(u)| \neq |p^{-1}(v)|$. Conversely, if $|p^{-1}(v)| = n$ for each $v \in V(\Gamma)$, then such a covering p is said to be *n-fold*. Each $p^{-1}(v)$ is called a *fibre* of $\tilde{\Gamma}$. An automorphism of $\tilde{\Gamma}$ which maps a fibre to a fibre is said to be *fibre-preserving*. The group K of all automorphisms of $\tilde{\Gamma}$ which fix each of the fibres setwise is called the *covering transformation group*. A covering $p : \tilde{\Gamma} \rightarrow \Gamma$ is said to be *regular* (simply, *A-covering*) if there is a subgroup A of K acting regularly on each fibre. Moreover, if Γ is connected, then $A = K$.

A purely combinatorial description of a covering was introduced through a voltage graph

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by Gross and Tucker [4,5] and also a very similar idea was appeared in Biggs' monograph [1,2]. Let A be a finite group. An (*ordinary*) *voltage assignment* (or, *A-voltage assignment*) of Γ is a function $\phi : A(\Gamma) \rightarrow A$ with the property that $\phi(u, v) = \phi(v, u)^{-1}$ for each $(u, v) \in A(\Gamma)$. The values of ϕ are called *voltages*, and A is called the *voltage group*. The *graph* $\Gamma \times_\phi A$ *derived from* ϕ is defined by $V(\Gamma \times_\phi A) = V(\Gamma) \times A$ and $E(\Gamma \times_\phi A) = \{((u, g), (v, \phi(u, v)g)) \mid (u, v) \in E(\Gamma), g \in A\}$. Clearly, the graph $\Gamma \times_\phi A$ is a covering of the graph Γ with the first coordinate projection $p : \Gamma \times_\phi A \rightarrow \Gamma$, which is called the *natural projection*. For each $u \in V(\Gamma)$, $\{(u, g) \mid g \in A\}$ is a fibre of $\Gamma \times_\phi A$. Moreover, by defining $(u, g')^g := (u, g'g)$ for any $g \in A$ and $(u, g') \in V(\Gamma \times_\phi A)$, A can be identified with a fibre-preserving automorphism subgroup of $\text{Aut}(\Gamma \times_\phi A)$ acting regularly on each fibre. Therefore, p can be viewed as a *A-covering*. Given a spanning tree T of the graph Γ , a voltage assignment ϕ is called *T-reduced* if the voltages on the tree arcs are identity. Gross and Tucker ([4]) showed that every regular covering of a graph Γ can be derived from an ordinary *T-reduced* voltage assignment ϕ with respect to an arbitrary fixed spanning tree T of Γ .

An automorphism α of Γ can be lifted to an automorphism $\tilde{\alpha}$ of a covering graph $\tilde{\Gamma}$ if $p\tilde{\alpha} = \alpha p$, where p is the covering projection from $\tilde{\Gamma}$ to Γ . We say a subgroup of H of $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted if each element of H can be lifted.

For a given finite connected graph Γ , a group H of automorphisms of Γ and a finite group A , a natural question can be raised as follows: Find all the connected regular coverings of Γ having A as its covering transformation group, on which each automorphism in H can be lifted. In [3], Du, Kawk and Xu investigate the regular coverings with $A = Z_p^n$, an elementary Abelian group and get some new matrix-theoretical characterizations for an automorphism of the base graph to be lifted, and as one of the applications, they gave a classification of all connected regular coverings of the Petersen graph with the covering transformation group Z_p^n , whose fibre-preserving automorphism subgroup acts arc-transitively.

In this paper, we use the same method to classify all the connected regular covering graphs of the cube satisfying the following two properties: (1) the covering transformation group is isomorphic to the elementary Abelian p -group; (2) the group of fibre-preserving automorphisms acts edge-transitively.

The cube is identified with the graph Γ as shown in Figure (a). Fix a spanning tree T in Γ as shown in Figure (b). Let $V_1 = \{2, 6, 4, 7, 3, 5\}$. Then the induced subgraph $\Gamma(V_1)$ is a line as shown in Figure (c).

Figure (a): the graph Γ ; (b) a spanning tree T of Γ .

Figure (c): the induced subgraph $\Gamma(V_1)$

First, we introduce five families of covering graphs $\Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_p^n$ of cube Γ by giving a T -reduced voltage assignment ϕ . Since ϕ is T -reduced, we only need to give the voltages on the cotree arcs (see Figure (c)). Let t denote the transposition of a matrix.

- (1) $X(2, 1) := \Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_2$, where $\phi_{26} = \phi_{47} = \phi_{35} = 1$ and $\phi_{46} = \phi_{37} = 0$,
 $X(p, 1) := \Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_p$, where $p = 3$ or $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, $\phi_{26} = \phi_{37} = 1$, $\phi_{46} = \phi_{35} = \frac{1+\sqrt{-3}}{2}$ and $\phi_{47} = 0$.
- (2) $X(p, 2) := \Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_p^2$, where $\phi_{26} = \phi_{37} = (0, 1)$, $\phi_{46} = \phi_{35} = (1, 0)$ and $\phi_{47} = (0, 0)$.
- (3) $X(p, 3) := \Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_p^3$, where $((\phi_{26})^t, (\phi_{47})^t, (\phi_{35})^t) = I_{3 \times 3}$, $\phi_{46} = (0, 1, -1)$ and $\phi_{37} = (-1, 1, 0)$.
- (4) $X(p, 4) := \Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_p^4$, where $p = 3$ or $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, $((\phi_{26})^t, (\phi_{46})^t, (\phi_{47})^t, (\phi_{37})^t) = I_{4 \times 4}$ and $\phi_{35} = (\frac{1-\sqrt{-3}}{2}, -1, \frac{1+\sqrt{-3}}{2}, \frac{1-\sqrt{-3}}{2})$.
- (5) $X(p, 5) := \Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_p^5$, where $((\phi_{26})^t, (\phi_{46})^t, (\phi_{47})^t, (\phi_{37})^t, (\phi_{35})^t) = I_{5 \times 5}$.

Now we state the main theorem of this paper.

Theorem 1.1 *Let $\tilde{\Gamma}$ be a connected regular covering of the cube Γ whose covering transformation group is isomorphic to Z_p^n and whose fibre-preserving automorphism subgroup G acts edge-transitively on $\tilde{\Gamma}$. Then, $\tilde{\Gamma}$ is isomorphic to one of the graphs in (1)-(5) listed above. Moreover, for the graphs $X(2, 1)$, $X(3, 1)$, $X(p, 2)$, $X(p, 3)$, $X(3, 4)$ and $X(p, 5)$, $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted, and so they are 2-arc-transitive; and for the graphs $X(p, 1)$ and $X(p, 4)$ for $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, the subgroup isomorphic to $A_4 \times Z_2$ can be lifted but $\text{Aut}\Gamma$ cannot, and so they are arc-transitive, in particular, all these five families of graphs are vertex transitive.*

§2. Algorithm for the Lifting

In this section, we present the algorithm given by Du, Kwak and Xu [3], which deals with the lifting problem for regular coverings of a graph Γ whose covering transformation group is elementary Abelian.

Throughout this section, let Γ be a connected graph and let $\tilde{\Gamma} = \Gamma \times_{\phi} Z_p^n$ be a connected regular covering of the Γ . The voltage group Z_p^n will be identified with the additive group of the n -dimensional vector space $V(n, p)$ over the finite field $GF(p)$. Since Γ is connected, the number $\beta(\Gamma) = |E(\Gamma)| - |V(\Gamma)| + 1$ is equal to the number of independent cycles in Γ and it is referred to as the *Betti number* of Γ .

Let $V(\Gamma) = \{0, 1, \dots, |V(\Gamma)| - 1\}$. For any arc $(i, j) \in A(\Gamma)$, by $\phi_{i,j}$ we denote the voltage on the arc, which is identified with a row vector in $V(n, p)$. An arc $(i, j) \in A(\Gamma)$ is called *positive* (resp. *negative*) if $i < j$ (resp. $i > j$). For each subset F in $E(\Gamma)$, we denote the set of its arcs, positive arcs and negative arcs by $A(F)$, $A^+(F)$ and $A^-(F)$, respectively, so that $A(F) = A^+(F) \cup A^-(F)$. In particular, if $F = E(\Gamma)$, we prefer to use $A(\Gamma)$, $A^+(\Gamma)$ and $A^-(\Gamma)$ to denote $A(F)$, $A^+(F)$ and $A^-(F)$, respectively. Fix a spanning tree T in the graph

Γ and let $E_0 = E(T)$, so that $|E(\Gamma) \setminus E_0|$ is the Betti number $\beta(\Gamma)$ of the graph Γ . From now on, the voltage assignment ϕ is assumed to be T -reduced. By the connectedness of $\tilde{\Gamma}$, $\{\phi_{i,j} \mid (i,j) \in A^+(E(\Gamma) \setminus E_0)\}$ generates the group Z_p^n . Hence, we get $n \leq \beta(\Gamma)$.

Let E_1 be a set of edges such that $\phi_{A^+(E_1)} = \{\phi_{i,j} \mid (i,j) \in A^+(E_1)\}$ is a basis for the vector space $V(n, p)$, and let $E_2 = E(\Gamma) \setminus (E_0 \cup E_1)$. Let

$$|E_0| = k, \quad |E_1| = n \quad \text{and} \quad |E_2| = m, \quad (1)$$

so that the number of edges in Γ is $k + n + m$.

Let Φ_0 (resp. Φ_1 and Φ_2) be the $k \times n$ (resp. $n \times n$ and $m \times n$) matrix with the row vectors $\phi_{i,j}$ for the arcs (i, j) in $A^+(E_0)$ (resp. $A^+(E_1)$ and $A^+(E_2)$), according to a fixed order of the positive arcs. Since the row vectors of Φ_1 form a basis for $V(n, p)$, there exists an $m \times n$ matrix M , called a *voltage generating matrix* of ϕ , such that

$$\Phi_2 = M\Phi_1. \quad (2)$$

Let

$$\Phi = \begin{pmatrix} \Phi_0 \\ \Phi_1 \\ \Phi_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

which is a $(k+n+m) \times n$ matrix over $GF(p)$, called a *voltage (assignment) matrix* corresponding to the voltage assignment ϕ . If we take $\phi_{A^+(E_1)}$ so that $\Phi_0 = \mathbf{0}$ and $\Phi_1 = I_{n \times n}$, the $n \times n$ identity matrix, then Φ is called a *reduced form* or a *T -reduced form* of the voltage assignment matrix Φ . From now on one may assume that Φ is in a reduced form without loss of any generality.

Let $\mathbf{V} = V(k+n+m, p)$ be the $(k+n+m)$ -dimensional row vector space over the field $GF(p)$. Hereafter, we denote a vector \mathbf{v} in \mathbf{V} by $(\mathbf{v}_0, \mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2) \in Z_p^k \oplus Z_p^n \oplus Z_p^m$, where the coordinates of the vector \mathbf{v}_0 (resp. \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2) are indexed by arcs in $A^+(E_0)$ (resp. $A^+(E_1)$ and $A^+(E_2)$), according to the same order of row vectors in Φ_0 (Φ_1 and Φ_2).

Given a graph Γ , its spanning tree T , and a positive cotree arc (u, v) , there is a unique path from v to u in T which is denoted by $[v, \dots, u]$. We call the closed walk $(u, [v, \dots, u])$ the *fundamental cycle* belonging to (u, v) , and denote it by $C(u, v; T)$. There are $n+m$ fundamental cycles in Γ , where $n+m$ is the Betti number of Γ .

Given a graph Γ and its spanning tree T , we keep the same order for positive arcs as the order of row vectors of the voltage matrix Φ . For each positive cotree arc (u, v) , let $\mathbf{p}^{u,v}$ be the k -dimensional row vector over $GF(p)$ whose (i, j) -coordinate $\mathbf{p}_{i,j}^{u,v}$ indexed by the positive tree arc (i, j) of the given order is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}_{i,j}^{u,v} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (i, j) \text{ is in } C(u, v; T), \\ -1 & \text{if } (j, i) \text{ is in } C(u, v; T), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Let P be the $(n+m) \times k$ matrix whose row vectors are $\mathbf{p}^{u,v}$, indexed by the positive cotree arcs (u, v) of the given order. We call P the *incidence matrix* for the fundamental cycles of the graph Γ with respect to the tree T .

Now we state the algorithm for solving lifting problem for the connected regular coverings of a graph Γ whose covering transformation group is elementary Abelian.

- (1st) Choose a fixed spanning tree T in Γ and write down the arcs in $A^+(E_0)$, $A^+(E_1)$ and $A^+(E_2)$ in a certain order so that $\Phi_0 = \mathbf{0}$, $\Phi_1 = I_{n \times n}$ and $\Phi_2 = M$.
- (2nd) Calculate the incidence matrix P for the fundamental cycles of Γ with respect to T .
- (3rd) Assume that the voltage generating matrix $M = (a_{ij})_{m \times n}$, where the entries a_{ij} are unknowns. Let $\Delta = ((-M, I_{m \times m})P, -M, I_{m \times m})$, whose columns are indexed by the arcs in $A^+(E_0), A^+(E_1), A^+(E_2)$ according to the given order. We call the matrix Δ the *discriminant matrix* for a lift of ϕ . For convenience, we write $\Delta_0 = (-M, I_{m \times m})P$, $\Delta_1 = -M$ and $\Delta_2 = I_{m \times m}$, so that $\Delta = (\Delta_0, \Delta_1, \Delta_2)$, as a block matrix.
- (4th) Let $\Delta = (\cdots, \mathbf{c}_{i,j}, \cdots)$, where $\mathbf{c}_{i,j}$ is the column indexed by $(i, j) \in A^+(\Gamma)$. For a given $\sigma \in \text{Aut}(\Gamma)$, let $\mathbf{c}_{i,j}^\sigma = \mathbf{c}_{i\sigma^{-1}, j\sigma^{-1}}$, where we assume that $\mathbf{c}_{i,j} = -\mathbf{c}_{j,i}$ for any arc (i, j) . Let $\Delta^\sigma = (\cdots, \mathbf{c}_{i,j}^\sigma, \cdots)$ for any $(i, j) \in A^+(\Gamma)$, and let $(\Delta^\sigma)_0$, $(\Delta^\sigma)_1$ and $(\Delta^\sigma)_2$ denote the first, the second and the third blocks of the matrix Δ^σ respectively, as before. Then one can say that

$$\sigma \text{ can be lifted} \iff (\Delta^\sigma)_1 + (\Delta^\sigma)_2 M = \mathbf{0} \iff \Delta_1^\sigma + \Delta_2^\sigma M = \mathbf{0}. \quad (5)$$

Proof of Theorem 1.1

Let $E_0 = E(T)$ and $E = E(\Gamma) \setminus E_0$. Give an ordering for the arcs in $A^+(E_0)$ and $A^+(E)$ as follows:

$$A^+(E_0) = \{15, 16, 17, 25, 28, 38, 48\},$$

$$A^+(E) = \{26, 46, 47, 37, 35\}.$$

Give fundamental cycles in Γ as follows:

$$C(2, 6; T) = (2, 6, 1, 5, 2),$$

$$C(4, 6; T) = (4, 6, 1, 5, 2, 8, 4),$$

$$C(4, 7; T) = (4, 7, 1, 5, 2, 8, 4),$$

$$C(3, 7; T) = (3, 7, 1, 5, 2, 8, 3),$$

$$C(3, 5; T) = (3, 5, 2, 8, 3).$$

It is well-known that $\text{Aut}(\Gamma) \cong S_4 \times Z_2$. Take four automorphisms of Γ as follows: $\alpha = (243)(567)$, $\beta = (14)(23)(58)(67)$, $\gamma = (18)(27)(36)(45)$ and $\delta = (23)(67)$.

It is easy to check that $M = \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ is subgroup of $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ isomorphic to A_4 , $N = \langle M, \gamma \rangle$ is subgroup of $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ isomorphic to $A_4 \times Z_2$, and $\langle N, \delta \rangle = \text{Aut}(\Gamma)$. Thus we have:

- (1) M can be lifted if and only if α and β can be lifted;
- (2) N can be lifted if and only if α , β and γ can be lifted;
- (3) $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted if and only if α , β , γ and δ can be lifted.

Since $\beta(\Gamma) = 5$, we get $n \leq 5$. If $n = 5$, then Γ is nothing but $X(p, 5)$ and by [6, Theorem 2.11], $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted. So, in what follows, we assume $n < 5$ and divide our proof into four cases for each n with $1 \leq n \leq 4$.

3.1 The Case of $n = 1$

Suppose that $n = 1$. Then $K = Z_p = V(1, p)$. Since the element (18)(25)(36)(47) of $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ maps 2, 6, 4, 7, 3, 5 to 5, 3, 7, 4, 6, 2, respectively, without loss of any generality, we have the following three essentially different cases for the set E_1 and E_2 :

- (1) $E_1 = \{26\}$ and $E_2 = \{46, 47, 37, 35\}$;
- (2) $E_1 = \{46\}$ and $E_2 = \{26, 47, 37, 35\}$;
- (3) $E_1 = \{47\}$ and $E_2 = \{26, 46, 37, 35\}$.

Case (1): $E_1 = \{26\}$ and $E_2 = \{46, 47, 37, 35\}$.

In this case, the incidence matrix is:

$$P = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} (1,5) & (1,6) & (1,7) & (2,5) & (2,8) & (3,8) & (4,8) \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} (2,6) \\ (4,6) \\ (4,7) \\ (3,7) \\ (3,5) \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let $D = (D_0, D_1, D_2)$ be the discriminant matrix with $D_0 = (-M, I_{4 \times 4})P$, $D_1 = (-M)$ and $D_2 = (I_{4 \times 4})$ with a voltage generating matrix $M = (a, b, c, d)^t$. A direct computation gives that $D_0 = (-M, I_{4 \times 4})P$ is equal to

$$D_0 = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} (1,5) & (1,6) & (1,7) & (2,5) & (2,8) & (3,8) & (4,8) \end{matrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} -a+1 & a-1 & 0 & a-1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ -b+1 & b & -1 & b-1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ -c+1 & c & -1 & c-1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ -d & d & 0 & d-1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

For an automorphism σ of Γ can be lifted if and only if

$$\Delta_1^\sigma + \Delta_2^\sigma M = (c_{26})^\sigma + (c_{46}c_{47}c_{37}c_{35})^\sigma M = \mathbf{0}. \quad (6)$$

Inserting $\alpha = (243)(567)$ to (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{0} &= D_1^\alpha + D_2^\alpha M = (c_{26})^\alpha + (c_{46}c_{47}c_{37}c_{35})^\alpha M \\ &= (c_{35}) + (c_{25}c_{26}c_{46}c_{47})M \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} a^2 - a - ab + c \\ ab - a - b^2 + d \\ ac - a - bc \\ ad - a - bd + 1 \end{pmatrix} = (x_{i,j}). \end{aligned}$$

Inserting $\beta = (14)(23)(58)(67)$ to (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{0} &= D_1^\beta + D_2^\beta M = (c_{26})^\beta + (c_{46}c_{47}c_{37}c_{35})^\beta M \\ &= (c_{37}) + (c_{17}c_{16}c_{26}c_{28})M \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} ab - b - ac + d \\ -a + b^2 - bc + d \\ -a + bc - c^2 + d + 1 \\ bd - cd + d \end{pmatrix} = (y_{ij}). \end{aligned}$$

Now assume that α and β can be lifted. By $y_{41} = 0$, we distinguish two cases: (1) $d = 0$; (2) $b - c + 1 = 0$. If (1) happens, by $x_{41} = 0$ and $x_{11} = 0$, we have $a = 1$ and $b = c$. But it doesn't satisfy $y_{21} = 0$. If (2) happens, by $y_{11} = 0$, we have $-a - b + d = 0$. By $x_{21} = 0$, we distinguish two subcases: (i) $a - b + 1 = 0$; (ii) $b = 0$. If (i) happens, by $(x_{ij}) = 0$, we have that either $a = c = 0$, $b = d = 1$ and $p = 2$ or $a = d = 2$, $b = 0$, $c = 1$ and $p = 3$. If (ii) happens, we have $c = 1$ and $a = d$. By $x_{11} = 0$, we have $a^2 - a + 1 = 0$. Thus the solution of $(x_{ij}) = (y_{ij}) = 0$ are: $a = c = 0$, $b = d = 1$ and $p = 2$; or $a = d = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{-3}}{2}$, $b = 0$, $c = 1$ and $p = 3$ or $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$. Or equivalently,

$$M_1 = (0, 1, 0, 1)^t, \quad p = 2;$$

$$M_{21} = \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{-3}}{2}, 0, 1, \frac{1 + \sqrt{-3}}{2} \right)^t, \quad p = 3 \text{ or } p \equiv 1 \pmod{6};$$

$$M_{22} = \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{-3}}{2}, 0, 1, \frac{1 - \sqrt{-3}}{2} \right)^t, \quad p = 3 \text{ or } p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}.$$

By $X(2, 1)$, $X(p, 1)$ and $X'(p, 1)$, we denote the covering graphs determined by M_1 , M_{21} and M_{22} , respectively. In particular, $X(p, 1)$ and $X'(p, 1)$ are the same one if $p = 3$.

Inserting $\gamma = (18)(27)(36)(45)$ to (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{0} &= D_1^\gamma + D_2^\gamma M = (c_{26})^\gamma + (c_{46}c_{47}c_{37}c_{35})^\gamma M \\ &= (c_{73}) + (c_{53}c_{52}c_{62}c_{64})M \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} b - ab + ac - d \\ b - b^2 + bc \\ b - bc + c^2 - 1 \\ -a + b - bd + cd \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, the matrices M_1 , M_{21} and M_{22} satisfy this equation and γ can be lifted, and so the group N can be lifted.

Inserting $\delta = (23)(67)$ to (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{0} &= D_1^\delta + D_2^\delta M = (c_{26})^\delta + (c_{46}c_{47}c_{37}c_{35})^\delta M \\ &= (c_{37}) + (c_{47}c_{46}c_{26}c_{25})M \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} b - ac + ad - d \\ a - bc + bd - d \\ -c^2 + cd - d + 1 \\ -cd + d^2 - d \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, the matrix M_1 satisfy this equation and δ can be lifted. But the matrices M_{21} and M_{22} satisfy this equation and δ can be lifted when $p = 3$. So, for graphs $X(2, 1)$ and $X(3, 1)$, $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted.

Finally, we show that for $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, the graphs $X(p, 1)$ and $X'(p, 1)$ are isomorphic as graphs. Let $V := V(X(p, 1)) = V(X'(p, 1)) = \{(i; x) \mid 1 \leq i \leq 8, x \in GF(p)\}$. Let $R = (\frac{-1+\sqrt{-3}}{2})$, and let $\zeta = (18)(25)(36)(47) \in \text{Aut}(\Gamma)$. Define a permutation Υ on V by $(i; x)^\Upsilon = (i^\zeta; (x)R)$. A direct checking shows that Υ is isomorphism from $X(p, 1)$ to $X'(p, 1)$.

Cases (2) and (3): By a computation similar to case (1), we can get the graph $X(p, 1)$ in case (2) and the graph $X(2, 1)$ in the case (3).

3.2 The case of $n = 2, 3,$ and 4

In this subsection, the case $n = 2, 3,$ and 4 will be described briefly.

Case $n = 2$. In the case, $K = Z_p^2 = V(2, p)$. As before, without loss we may assume one of the following happens:

- (1) $E_1 = \{46, 37\}$ and $E_2 = \{26, 47, 35\}$;
- (2) $E_1 = \{26, 46\}$ and $E_2 = \{47, 37, 35\}$;
- (3) $E_1 = \{26, 47\}$ and $E_2 = \{46, 37, 35\}$;
- (4) $E_1 = \{26, 37\}$ and $E_2 = \{46, 47, 35\}$;
- (5) $E_1 = \{26, 35\}$ and $E_2 = \{46, 47, 37\}$;
- (6) $E_1 = \{46, 47\}$ and $E_2 = \{26, 37, 35\}$.

For the case of (1), let

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \\ a_3 & b_3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

be a voltage generating matrix. Then a computation similar to case $n = 1$ gives that $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted if and only if $a_1 = a_2 = b_2 = b_3$ and $b_1 = a_3 = 1$. Accordingly, we can get the graph $X(p, 2)$.

In the Cases of (2), (3), (4), (5) and (6), the group M can not be lifted.

Case $n = 3$. In this case, $K = Z_p^3 = V(3, p)$. Without any loss of generality, we may assume one of the following happens:

- (1) $E_1 = \{26, 47, 35\}$ and $E_2 = \{46, 37\}$;
- (2) $E_1 = \{26, 46, 47\}$ and $E_2 = \{37, 35\}$;
- (3) $E_1 = \{26, 46, 37\}$ and $E_2 = \{47, 35\}$;
- (4) $E_1 = \{26, 46, 35\}$ and $E_2 = \{47, 37\}$;
- (5) $E_1 = \{46, 47, 37\}$ and $E_2 = \{26, 35\}$;
- (6) $E_1 = \{26, 47, 37\}$ and $E_2 = \{46, 35\}$.

For the case of (1), one can show that $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted if and only if the voltage generation matrix

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Thus, we get the graph $X(p, 3)$.

In the case (2), (3), (4), (5) and (6), the group M can not be lifted.

Case $n = 4$. In this case, $K = Z_p^4 = V(4, p)$. Without any loss of generality, we may divide our discussion into mutually exclusive three cases as followings:

Case (1): $E_1 = \{26, 46, 47, 37\}$ and $E_2 = \{35\}$.

Let $D = (D_0, D_1, D_2)$ be the discriminant matrix with $D_0 = (-M, I_{1 \times 1})P$, $D_1 = (-M)$ and $D_2 = (I_{1 \times 1})$ with a voltage generating matrix $M = (a, b, c, d)$.

The group $\text{Aut}(\Gamma)$ can be lifted if and only if

$$M_1 = \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{-3}}{2}, -1, \frac{1 + \sqrt{-3}}{2}, \frac{1 - \sqrt{-3}}{2} \right), \quad p = 3 \text{ or } p \equiv 1 \pmod{6};$$

$$M_2 = \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{-3}}{2}, -1, \frac{1 - \sqrt{-3}}{2}, \frac{1 + \sqrt{-3}}{2} \right), \quad p = 3 \text{ or } p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}.$$

By $X(p, 4)$ and $X'(p, 4)$, we denote the covering graphs determined by M_1 and M_2 , respectively. In particular, $X(p, 4)$ and $X'(p, 4)$ are the same one if $p = 3$.

For $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, the graphs $X(p, 4)$ and $X'(p, 4)$ are isomorphic as graphs. Let $V :=$

$V(X(p, 4)) = V(X'(p, 4)) = \{(i; x, y, z, w) \mid 1 \leq i \leq 8, x, y, z, w \in GF(p)\}$. Let

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} c_2 - 1 & 1 & -c_2 & c_2 - 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

And let and let $\zeta = (18)(25)(36)(47) \in \text{Aut}(\Gamma)$. Define a permutation Υ on V by $(i; x, y, z, w)^\Upsilon = (i^\zeta; (x, y, z, w)R)$. A direct checking shows that Υ is isomorphism from $X(p, 4)$ to $X'(p, 4)$.

Case (2): $E_1 = \{26, 46, 47, 35\}$ and $E_2 = \{37\}$, and $\{\phi_{26}, \phi_{46}, \phi_{47} \phi_{37}\}, \{\phi_{46}, \phi_{47}, \phi_{37} \phi_{35}\}$ are linear dependant, hence letting

$$M = (0, b, c, 0).$$

Now, one can show that M cannot be lifted.

By a similar computation, in case (3), $E_1 = \{26, 46, 37, 35\}$ and $E_2 = \{47\}$, and the group M can not be lifted.

Combining subsection 3.1 and 3.2, we finish the proof of Theorem 1.1. \square

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